

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD INDUSTRY IN ENSURING OF THE FOOD SECURITY

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Abstract

Every country's food security is important for its economic and national security. Providing the population with food products is one of the most important socio-economic problems. Food safety is one of the priority directions of the policy of every state. Thus, it is important to take extensive socio-economic measures to solve this problem. The socio-economic system in every country is closely related to food security. Ensuring food safety is based on the mobilization of domestic resources. In this regard, a broad strategy of economic reforms is being developed, many measures are being taken related to sustainable development and improvement of the living conditions of the population.

It should be noted that food safety at the human level is the basis of sustainable development. Sustainable development is based on balanced consumption of natural resources.

Keywords: food security, food industry, economy, food products.

Providing the population with food products and raw materials has an important socio-political and economic importance. At the same time, it is a special guarantee of the socio-economic security of the society. Therefore, every state develops a scientifically based concept to provide the population with quality food products, and this concept forms the basis of the strategic line of the state's socio-economic policy.

The process of industrialization plays a special role in the development of the economy of each country. Comprehensive development of the economy is possible through balanced development. The world experience shows that the process of balanced management of the fields is possible by ensuring the development of the economy in all directions.

The crises occurring in the world, economic security, including food safety problems, reveal the relevance of this topic. At present, one can see how risky the problem of food security is in some countries of the world. Food shortage remains one of the main threats to national security. In order to prevent such situations from happening, fundamental reform is being carried out in every country. Examples of this include industrial parks, industrial technology parks, agricultural parks, innovation centers, and the development of small and medium-sized enterprises.

It is known that as the economy develops, the rise of the country is also realized. Economic development manifests itself at the expense of a number of natural resources of the country or according to the level of development of intellectual property. One of the main areas of its economy is the concept of industrial economy. Today, both developed and developing countries attach special importance to the industrial economy. One of the main, important areas of the industrial economy is the food industry. In all countries, the food industry is the main provider of the country's food security.

Of course, the food industry is a cooperation system of the integration of the agricultural sector and the processing industry. The development of the processing industry is characterized by its own character-

istics. On the other hand, industrialization acts as a driving force of the agricultural sector. The investment potential formed in the agricultural sector is one of the factors that ensure the development of industrialization. In turn, the industrial sector provides agriculture with production technologies, and by increasing the demand for agricultural products, it creates the basis for increasing the profit of this sector.

Studies show that the relations between agriculture and industry have been analyzed in economic literature in most cases. However, when both areas are examined, it becomes clear that agriculture and processing industry ensure each other's development.

Lin and Koo, who investigated the interdependence between China's agricultural and industrial sectors in 1952-1988, found that the Chinese agricultural sector had an impact on industrial development, but the growth in the industrial sector did not lead to any development in the agricultural sector. As the reason for this, they indicated that China adopted a socialist development strategy during that period, which included industrialization over the development of agriculture. However, research shows that Lin and Koo's evaluation of the dependence between industry and agriculture was not comprehensive, and some shortcomings were observed. Thus, they did not take into account foreign trade, which is an important factor during this evaluation. (13)

According to Dilip Shaikian, agriculture and industry are integral parts of development and both of them are interdependent and related. Also, in most developing countries, the impact of agriculture on the economy as a whole, as well as on the industrial sector, is an undeniable fact. However, according to him, this dependence between industry and agriculture can and does change over time. He notes that different directions of interaction between industry and agriculture have been reflected in various theoretical and empirical literatures. (3)

80% of the raw material needs of food industry enterprises are covered only by agricultural products.

Rosenstein-Rodan, Lewis, Scitovsky, Hirschman, Jorgeson, Fei and Ranis note that agriculture supplies industry with products and raw materials, as well as cheap labor. According to them, the strategy of accelerating agricultural industrialization in developing countries is simply acts as an addition. (10)

A. Chayanov also justified the necessity of development of cooperative relations connecting the production, processing and sale of agricultural products in his works.

Food security is one of the important problems faced by the countries of the world at all stages of development of the society. Its importance has increased even more in the age of modern innovations. Because food products are the most important condition for a person to live. K. Marx notes that people are involved in politics, science, religion, art, etc. to deal with, first of all, they have to eat, drink, dress and have an apartment to live in. Therefore, the production of food products is a condition for the existence of human society. Marx also shows that "the production of food products is the first and main condition for the subsistence of producers and for all production in general" .

It should be noted that nature does not provide ready-made food products necessary for people's survival. Therefore, people are forced to produce all the food products and other items necessary for their vital needs in order to survive.

In a situation where the world's population is growing rapidly and natural resources are running out, the issue of food security manifests itself more acutely. The division of the world into developed (rich) and developing (poor) regions indicates a violation of social justice. Even in the most optimistic forecasts, it is not excluded that the number of hungry people on the planet will drop in the next ten years.

The specificity of the food industry as a subject of the economy is expressed by the fact that it is organically related to the need to provide the country's population with high-quality food products at this level of development of the agricultural sector and solvent demand. The country's food security is highly dependent on the efficiency of the food industry. The modern level of the food industry is the result of centuries-old development trends and laws of society.

One of the main issues that hinders the successful implementation of food security programs and the achievement of the desired results from them is the sudden transformation of the peasants into the owners of the land thanks to the implemented land reforms, in other words, from the status of being managed to the status of managers.

The food industry is one of the largest and main branches of the industry, which includes areas and sub-areas that provide food consumed by the population. For the strong development of the food industry, first of all, stable raw materials should be taken into account. The source of development of the fields and sub-fields that include the food industry is raw materials. In this regard, ensuring food safety in all countries is considered one of the priority tasks of the state. Accordingly, the most effective ways of ensuring food security, ways

of improving interaction mechanisms between agriculture and food industry are determined based on the creation of various regional associations and complexes in all countries.

Each country solves the problem of food safety by eliminating external and internal threats. Different versions of the food insecurity problem are proposed in the economic literature. Why is food safety a must? As a reason for this, the decrease in the volume of production of food products, the increase in the volume of import of food products, the decrease in the production potential of the agro-industrial complex, etc. shown. Ushachev I.G. noted that natural disasters (drought, floods, etc.), deepening stratification in society and increasing the weight (share) of the low-income population are among the factors that determine food security in agriculture. (15)

Khromov Y.S. gave an example of low-quality, dangerous food products imported into the list of foreign factors. (7)

Food security depends on internal and external factors. Identifying these factors in ensuring food safety determines the state's strategy. The following are the main internal factors affecting the country's food security:

- the structure of cultivated fields
- fodder problem in animal husbandry
- low use of the production potential of the agricultural sector;
- in processing industrial enterprises monopoly;
- poor development of production and market infrastructure;
- market principles adaptation;
- financial problems;
- losses
- obsolescence of equipment
- low income level of the population;

External factors hindering food security:

- import exceeding export;
- the world market price conjuncture for food products imported by the country effect;
- from water resources dependence;
- unfavorable conditions of food trade with foreign countries,

The main goal of every state is to reduce these threats. Each state has a strategy that is aimed at solving food-related problems to one degree or another.

The main condition of food security is self-sufficiency. Self-sufficiency is meeting the demand for food products at the expense of domestic production.

If we understand the provision of food security in the world as a global problem, we should try to solve this problem together with other global problems. I would like to mention several solutions to ensure food security.

1. Effective use of arable land
2. Further increasing the role of the national economy in ensuring food security and reducing its dependence on the international market;
3. To create a common state fund. To use this fund to strengthen the food safety of the countries of the world or in emergency situations.

3. Development of the norm for conducting the correct assessment.
4. To develop the employment level of the population
5. Take global measures to prevent environmental pollution
6. Effective use of natural resources.
7. Creation of planned and regulated production relations

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